

Adsorption kinetics modeling of benzene from aqueous solution onto rice husk activated carbon prepared by H₃PO₄ activation

S. M. Yakout

Biochemistry Department, College of Science, King Saud University, P.O. Box 2455, Riyadh 11451, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Hot Laboratories Centre, Atomic Energy Authority, Cairo 13759, Egypt

E-mail : sobhy.yakout@gmail.com Fax : 966-14675932

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Abstract : Benzene is one of the most hazardous organic pollutants in groundwater. The removal of benzene from water is very important from health point of view and for environmental protection. Activated carbon from rice husk (RHC) with H₃PO₄ activation was used to study batch aqueous benzene remediation kinetics. The adsorption profile showed an initial rapid uptake of benzene which decreased and became almost constant after 40 min of contact at which up to 80% benzene was removed from water. Different rate-based and diffusion-based kinetic models were adopted to understand the benzene adsorption mechanism on RHC. Three typical kinetic models namely, pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order and Elovich equations, were applied to interpret the kinetic data. The rate constants have been determined and the correlation coefficients have been calculated in order to assess which model provides the best fit predicted data with experimental results. The pseudo-second order models were well fitted to the kinetic data ($R^2 = 0.98$), thereby indicating that chemisorption. To investigate the rate determining step, the intra-particle diffusion and Boyd model was applied on the experimental data. External mass transport with intra-particle diffusion phenomena governed the rate limiting process, which has been confirmed from the Boyd poor non-linear kinetic plots. A comparative study on the benzene adsorption revealed that the RHC had better benzene adsorption capacity (365 mg/g) as compared to CNTs and other granular activated carbon. This suggests that the RHC are efficient benzene adsorbents and that they possess good potential for benzene removal in wastewater treatment.

Keywords : Benzene, adsorption kinetics, rice husk, chemical activation.

Introduction

Benzene is one of the most toxic aromatic hydrocarbons and its removal from wastewater and gasoline in different industrial processes is very important for environmental protection. In the United States, gasoline is generally composed of 2% benzene by volume but the concentration of benzene in gasoline may be up to 5% in other countries¹. It should be noted that benzene, with a water solubility of 1780 mg/L, is more water soluble than other major gasoline components. Therefore, if accidental leakage occurs from an underground gasoline storage tank, benzene would pose a serious threat to the groundwater system and the public who drink the benzene contaminated groundwater for a long time would be potentially at risk of developing cancer risk. The United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and Tai-

wan EPA have both set the maximum contaminant level for benzene in drinking water and groundwater at 0.005 mg/L².

A considerable effort has been dedicated in the past years concerning the removal of these compounds from wastewater, several methods have been proposed and developed, and the most extensively used is adsorption process³. For this purpose, various types of adsorbent have been used for removal of these organic compounds and adsorption on activated carbon is a proven, reliable technology for removal of small quantities of soluble organic compounds from water or wastewater. Also activated carbon adsorption has been cited by the US Environmental Protection Agency as one of the best available environmental control technologies⁴.

Rice husk (RH) is an agricultural by-product abundantly available in rice producing countries. They are the natural sheaths that form on rice grains during their growth. The estimated annual world rice production is about 571 million tonnes resulting in approximately 140 million tonnes of rice husk available annually for utilization⁵. In Egypt, rice husk is one of the most important agricultural residues in quantity⁶. Traditionally, rice husks have been disposed in landfill or used as a bedding material for animals. However, industrial applications of this material are limited. Most of the rice husks are left in rural areas or rice processing plants, with little application in industry. The most common method for disposal of rice husk (RH) is incineration on farms. This produces ash, fumes, and toxic organic gases, leading to serious air pollution. The rice husk with hard surface, high silicon content and small bulk density cannot be easily decomposed by bacteria. So, it is a dramatic source of pollution and leads to a series of environmental problems including eutrophication⁷. If we cannot utilize in an appropriate approach to exploit rice husk, the hazardous materials will be released into the environment, thereby causing numerous problems that cannot be ignored⁸. The processing and transformation of rice husks into activated carbon with good adsorption properties would alleviate problems of disposal and management of these waste by-products, while producing value added products from rice husks for water and wastewater treatment, etc. to expand the carbon market. According recent review on activated carbon from rice husk, chemical activation with KOH, NaOH, Na₂CO₃, K₂CO₃, H₃PO₄ at different temperatures for various times were used for activation⁹. Recently, since phosphoric acid has some environmental advantages such as ease of recovery, low energy cost and high carbon, it is used for the preparation of good carbon adsorbents from rice husks¹⁰⁻¹⁴. Rice husk-based activated carbons have the ability for removal of metal ions¹³ and organic molecules^{11,12} from aqueous phase adsorption.

Today, adsorption kinetic study still attracts considerable interest because of its particular significance in adsorbent evaluation and application, and more deliberate but complicated models will be proposed on the basis of adsorption mechanism and diffusion analysis. In this work, analyses and batch adsorption experiments have been carried out to characterize and to understand adsorption

mechanism by modeling the adsorption kinetic. The aim of the present paper was to study the possibility of the removal of benzene by rice husk activated carbon. A kinetic study according to different models has been applied. Using batch studies, the rate constants and the reaction order have been calculated.

Material and methods :

Analytical grade benzene with >99% purity was purchased from Merck. A stock solution in methanol (Sigma-Aldrich, puriss p.a. >99.8%-GC) was prepared in 10 mL volumetric flasks containing 2000 ppm from each of the above-mentioned contaminants, using microliter syringes. The aqueous standard was prepared by spiking a measured quantity of methanol standard into 100 mL volumetric flask filled with reagent water. These solutions were used for the kinetics experiments.

Activated carbon preparation :

Rice husk was obtained from local rice mills and was washed several times with bi-distilled water followed by filtration. Rice husk carbon (RHC) was prepared according procedures in previous work with some modification¹⁵. The rice husk was mixed with phosphoric acid (50 wt%) in a mass ratio (rice husk to phosphoric acid) of 1 : 4, then the mixture slightly agitated to ensure penetration of the acid throughout, then the mixture heated to 80 °C for 1 h and left overnight at room temperature to help appropriate wetting and impregnation of the precursor. The impregnated mass was heated gradually up to 700 °C within 1 h in a steel pipe (furnace tube), and soaked at this temperature for 2 h. After cooling the carbonized mass was washed several times with bidistilled water (95 °C) until pH 6.5 and dried at 110 °C. The resulting solid product was named as RHC.

Characterization :

Elemental analysis of sorbent materials was performed by CHN Elemental Analyzer (Perkin-Elmer, Norwath, USA). Surface area of activated carbon was determined using Quantachrome NOVA 1100e by nitrogen adsorption method after degassing for 1 h at 105 °C. The Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method was used to calculate the surface area, based on selected N₂ adsorption data within the p/p^0 range of 0.025–0.3³¹. The total pore volumes estimated from the volume of nitrogen adsorbed

at $p/p^{\circ} = 0.95$ (V_p) and an average pore radius from $r = 2 V_p/SBET$. The surface organic functional groups were investigated by a Fourier transform infrared spectrometer (IRPrestige-21, Japan). The scanning electron micrographs (SEM) was obtained using SEM model JSM 5910 (JEOL, Japan).

Kinetic study :

Kinetics experiments were carried out using 110 mL glass bottles with addition of 50 mg of RHC and 100 mL of benzene solution of initial concentrations (C_0) of 200 mg/L, which were chosen to be representative of maximum benzene concentration in an industrial wastewater. Mixture was filtered and C_e was measured after different intervals of time (0–300 min) until the residual concentration remains constant. Benzene concentration before and after adsorption were determined by Purge & Trap (model : HP-7695) Gas chromatography (model : HP-6890) with flame ionization detector (PT-GC-FID) according to US-EPA (524.2) method¹⁶. Sorption capacity of adsorbent was calculated by :

$$q_e = V(C_0 - C_e)/m \quad (1)$$

where C_0 and C_e are the initial and equilibrium concentration (mg/L) respectively, M is the mass of dry carbon sample used (g) and V volume of solution (ml).

Results and discussion

The rice husk used was a locally available material in Egypt. It had the following approximate dimensions¹⁷ : 8–10 mm long, 2.0–2.5 mm wide and 0.1–0.15 mm thick. The RH sample was analyzed according to standard ASTM : D-3172-73 method and was found to contain 64.3% volatile matter, 15.9% fixed carbon and 19.8% ash. Moreover, the main constituents of the metallic residues (ash content) are : silica 94.5%, calcium oxide 0.25%, magnesium oxide 0.23%, sodium oxide 0.78%, potassium oxide 1.10%, ferric oxide trace (< 0.5), phosphorous pentoxide 0.53% and sulfur oxide 0.6%¹⁷.

Preparation of RHC :

Phosphoric acid activation process is preferred because it does not entail the problems with corrosion, inefficient chemical recovery, and other environmental disadvantages that are associated with $ZnCl_2$ ¹⁸. Additionally, the presence of H_3PO_4 in the interior of the precursor can restrict the formation of tar species and inhibit

the shrinkage of the precursor particle by occupying certain substantial volumes¹⁹. More favorably, after activation phosphoric acid can be easily washed away with water, and have rich in containing phosphorus groups on the surface of activated carbons²⁰. There has been very little study focusing on the use of H_3PO_4 as a chemical activating agent for rice husk. According Somasundaram *et al.* (2013), when RH was applied to the activation after impregnated with phosphoric acid, it leads to the following reaction scheme²¹ :

Eq. (2) represents the reaction between RH and phosphoric acid. This reaction occurred at room temperature and was completed within an hour²². In fact, phosphoric acid reacts as soon as it is mixed with RH. The reaction does not lead however to a loss of mass. Eq. (3) is the evaporation of water contained in the sample. Eq. (4) exemplifies the chemical transformation of phosphoric acid into P_2O_5 via water desorption. As the temperature increases, phosphoric acid is converted into several species, such as pyrophosphoric acid and polyphosphoric acid by condensation, dehydration and eventually into P_2O_5 ²³. As a result, reaction (4) is a simplified formulation of a series of more complex chemical reactions. Eq. (5) stands for the evaporation of P_2O_5 . This component vaporizes at a temperature between 580 and 585 °C. Eq. (6) illustrates the pyrolysis of the $RH-H_3PO_4$ into char and volatile compounds. Finally, the release of light gases from char is taken into account by eq. (7), which results in the formation of defined pores. Thus, phosphoric acid acts as a catalyst for depolymerisation of the constituents of the lignocellulosic precursor into smaller units. During the chemical activation of lignocellulosic precursors, the phosphoric acid forms phosphate and polyphosphate bridges that connect the biopolymer fragments avoiding contraction of the material by the effect of the temperature. As a result, the mechanical properties of the material are strengthened²⁴.

RHC characterization :

Efficiency of sorbent is mainly dependent on surface area and binding forces present within the particles of sorbent, as well as chemical characteristics of sorbate. Table 1 illustrates the physicochemical characteristics of activated carbon. Lower ash content (3.8%) reflected in its lower density. The pH measurements indicate that RHC is acidic in nature (2.1). Micropore volume represents

Table 1. Physicochemical characteristics of RHC

Physical characterization		Chemical characterization	
Inner BET surface area (m ² /g)	1446	pH	2.5
Total pore volume (cm ³ /g)	2.3	C%	68.5
Mean pore radius (nm)	3.1	H%	6.3
Micro pore volume (cm ³ /g)	1.9	N%	1.9
Density (g/ml)	0.447	Cl%	1.1
Water content (% wt)	9	S%	2.6
		Ash content	5.8

about 82% of the total pore volume. Iodine number of RHC (875 mg/g) is lower than its BET surface area (1446 m²/g). The iodine number gives an indication of the adsorption capacity of activated carbon in micropores and provided a good indication of surface area of an activated carbon²⁵. This can be due to iodine molecule has an area of about 0.15–0.42 nm², therefore can pass through mesopores and fit into micropores of adsorbent particles providing information about the internal surface.

Spectroscopic results, suggested that the RHC contain a mixture of oxides and sulfur compounds. The infrared absorption spectrum of the RHC exhibits a very broad bonded -OH stretching at 3418 cm⁻¹. Presence of absorption band at 1183 cm⁻¹ may be due to C–O bond²⁶. The absorption band at 1587 cm⁻¹ can be assigned to carbonyl group (C=O)²⁷. The presence of sulphoxide group (S=O) is indicated by the band observed at 1036 cm⁻¹. The carbon skeleton may be due to aliphatic compounds represented by C–H (stretch.) at 2852 and 2917 cm⁻¹. This interpretation of the spectrum is in fair agreement with the results obtained from the elemental analysis, which are given in Table 1.

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) photograph of RHC progressive changes in the surface of the cellular structure of the parent material with H₃PO₄ solution used. The cellulosic units are hydrolyzed by the acid and thus

the main components of the inter cellular wall are broken down to smaller structure, thus it is apparent that the external surface of RHC is quite rough, consisting of cavities, cracks, and irregular protrusion.

Fig. 2. Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) photographs of RHC at 1 × 500 magnifications.*Adsorption profile :*

The adsorption profile of benzene uptake with time is shown in Fig. 3, where a plot of amount of benzene adsorbed versus contact time is depicted. The removal curves are single, smooth and continuous leading to saturation, suggesting possible monolayer coverage of benzene molecules on the surface of the RHC adsorbent. Benzene removal increases with time and attain equilibrium at 40 min. Short equilibrium time is one of the important considerations for economical wastewater treatment applications. A quick glance at Fig. 3 reveals two sections of the uptake profile which are (i) the initial

Fig. 3. Benzene adsorption profile on RHC.

rapid uptake of benzene between 0 and 30 min and (ii) a more gradual process that comes to an equilibrium state after 40 min of contact. No further uptake of benzene by RHC was observed after the equilibrium time of 40 min. The initial rapid adsorption of benzene molecules on RHC is due to the availability of larger number of vacant adsorption sites for the benzene of the bulk solution. The subsequent slower adsorption is likely because of the competition among the benzene for the limited number of vacant adsorption sites. Thus the driving concentration gradient between the bulk solution and the solid surface is the main factor controlling the kinetics of the system. A similar trend of rapid initial and subsequent slower adsorption was reported by many researchers^{4,28,29}. The initial slopes of Fig. 3 show that the uptake rate of benzene by RHC is greatly dependent on the initial benzene concentration. The rapid adsorption rates indicate that the predominant mechanism for benzene adsorption on RHC is film diffusion which is activated by the high concentration difference between the bulk solution and the pores of the adsorbent.

Kinetic study :

Every adsorption process may follow one or their combination from different patterns such as chemical reaction, diffusion control and mass transfer. Analysis of experimental data at various time make possible to calculate the kinetic parameters, and take some information for designing and modeling the adsorption processes. To understand the adsorption mechanism of RHC for benzene, the adsorption kinetics were investigated using

pseudo-first order³⁰, pseudo-second order³¹ and Elovich kinetic equation³² models. Listed models are respectively presented by the following equations :

$$\log (q_e - q_t) = \log (q_e) - \frac{k_1}{2.303} t \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e} \quad (9)$$

$$q_t = \frac{1}{\beta} \ln (\alpha\beta) + \frac{1}{\beta} \ln t \quad (10)$$

where q_e and q_t (mg g^{-1}) and are the amount of benzene adsorbed at equilibrium and time t respectively. k_1 (min^{-1}) and k_2 (g/mg min) are the rate constant of pseudo-first and pseudo-second order rate adsorption, α ($\text{mg g}^{-1} \text{min}$) is the initial adsorption rate and β (g/mg) is the desorption constant. The experimental kinetic results were modeled to above mentions situations and their estimated parameters values are shown in Table 2. The conformity between experimental data and the model predicted val-

Table 2. Kinetic parameters of benzene adsorption onto RHC

Model	Parameter	Value
Experimental data	$q_{e,\text{exp}}$ (mg/g)	365
First-order	K_1 (g/mg min)	38.2×10^{-3}
	q_e (mg/g)	316
	R^2	0.92
Second-order	K_2 (g/mg min)	0.125×10^{-3}
	q_e (mg/g)	400
	R^2	0.98
Elovich	α (mg/g min)	4.4
	β (g/mg)	10.4×10^{-3}
	R^2	0.9
Intra-particle diffusion	k_{id} (mg/g min ^{1/2})	31.4
	C	114.7
	R^2	0.94

ues was expressed by the correlation coefficients and between two first models another judgment is based on the agreement between experimental and theoretical experimental value. The result indicates that the pseudo-second order model ($R^2 = 0.98$) is more suitable than the pseudo-first order kinetic model ($R^2 = 0.92$) and Elovich model ($R^2 = 0.9$) for benzene adsorption on RHC, and that the adsorption complies with the pseudo-second order reac-

tion. These results clear in Figs. 4–6. The calculated q_e values obtained from the first order kinetic model do not give responsible values, which are too low compared with experimental q_e values. Estimated q_e values of pseudo-second order model accurately predict the adsorption kinetics over the entire working times. Therefore, this model has enough sufficiency for precise and acceptable accurate prediction of the kinetics of benzene adsorption onto RHC. This suggested the overall rate of the adsorption process is most likely to be controlled by the chemisorption process³³ and rate of reaction is directly proportional to the number of active sites on the surface of adsorbent. According to pseudo-second order model, the adsorption rate dq_t/dt is proportional to the second order of $(q_e - q_t)$.

Fig. 4. Pseudo-first order plot for the adsorption of benzene by RHC.

Fig. 5. Pseudo-second order plot for the adsorption of benzene by RHC.

Fig. 6. Elovich kinetic plot for the adsorption of benzene by RHC.

Since RHC have relatively high equilibrium adsorption density q_e , the adsorption rates become very fast and the equilibrium times are short. Such short equilibrium times coupled with high adsorption capacity indicate high degree of affinity between adsorbate molecules and carbon surface³⁴.

Adsorption kinetics mechanism :

The adsorption in which an adsorbate is adsorbed from the liquid phase onto the adsorbent particles involves three steps. First step is the film diffusion stage, in which the adsorbate diffuses from the aqueous bulk solution to the external surface of sorbent particles. The second step is called the intraparticle diffusion stage, during which the adsorbate diffuses from the outer surface into the particle interior through the pores. The third step is the adsorption of the adsorbate at an internal site. The overall rate of adsorption depends on the slowest stage in the above process. The third step is being very rapid in nature and cannot be taken into account for the rate determining step³⁵. The pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order, and Elovich kinetic models cannot generally identify the diffusion mechanism and rate-controlling steps that affect the adsorption. In order to understand the rate controlling step, the experimental data was subjected to the following different models :

Intraparticle diffusion study (Weber and Morris model) :

The model of intraparticle diffusion is of great concern because it plays a significant role in the rate determining step in the equilibrium adsorption process. The

rate constants of intraparticle diffusion (k_{id}) were determined by using the following equation³⁶ and are depicted in Table 2.

$$q_t = k_{id} t^{0.5} \quad (11)$$

where k_{id} (mg/g min^{0.5}) represents the intraparticle diffusion rate constant and its values are obtained from a plot of q vs $t^{0.5}$ (Fig. 7). The 'C' values are obtained from the intercept of the plot and represent a constant depicting resistance to mass transfer in the boundary layer. The

Fig. 7. Intraparticle diffusion for the adsorption of benzene on RHC.

larger the value of C , the greater is the boundary layer effect. For pure intraparticle diffusion to take place, the plot of q vs $t^{0.5}$ should be linear passing through the origin with no intercept. But if the plot shows multilinearity, then the adsorption process may be controlled by the combination of film and intraparticle diffusion, i.e. more than one step is involved in the adsorption process³⁷.

When the benzene kinetic data was analyzed according to the intraparticle diffusion described by Weber and Morris³⁸, it was observed that the adsorption profile can be separated into three sections as shown in Fig. 7. According to Onal *et al.*³⁹, the three stages involves an initial sharper portion which is attributed to the diffusion of adsorbate through the solution to the external surface of the adsorbent or the boundary layer diffusion of solute molecules. The second portion describes the gradual adsorption stage, in which intraparticle diffusion may be rate limiting. The third stage involves the diffusion of

sorbate particles to adsorption sites. The adsorption mechanism can frequently be controlled by multi-diffusion steps, involving film diffusion and intraparticle diffusion⁴⁰. It may be concluded that surface adsorption and intraparticle diffusion were concurrently operating during the RHC and benzene interactions⁴¹.

The intercepts obtained by the extrapolation of the second portion of the plots back towards the y-axis shows intraparticle diffusion is not the only controlling step of the process because the plot does not pass through the origin. This deviation may be due to the difference in mass transfer rate in the initial and final stages of adsorption. The intraparticle diffusion rate constant (k_{id}) obtained from the linear portions of the plots is depicted in Table 2. Similar observations were reported by many researchers while studying the adsorption behavior of different substrates.

Boyd model :

In order to characterize the actual rate-controlling step involved in the adsorption of benzene by RHC, the adsorption data were further analyzed according to the kinetic expression developed by Boyd *et al.*⁴². If the rate-determining step is diffusion through the adsorbent, then the following equation is valid.

$$F = 1 - (6/\pi^2) \exp(-B_t) \quad (12)$$

and

$$F = \frac{q_t}{q_\infty} \quad (13)$$

where q_t represents the amount of metal adsorbed (mg/g) at any time t (min), q_∞ is the amount of metal adsorbed at infinite time (mg/g), F represents the fraction of solute adsorbed at any time t , B_t is a mathematical function of F , was calculated for each value of F employing Reichenburg equation :

$$B_t = -0.4977 - \ln(1 - F) \quad (14)$$

The linearity test of B_t vs time plots was employed to distinguish between the film diffusion- and particle diffusion-controlled adsorption. If the plot of B_t vs time (having slope B) is a straight line passing through the origin, then the adsorption rate is governed by particle diffusion mechanism otherwise it is governed by film diffusion⁴³. The t versus B_t plots are presented in Fig. 8. The plot was linear for benzene sorption up to 80 min from the aque-

Fig. 8. Boyd kinetic model for the adsorption of benzene on RHC.

ous solution onto RHC. The straight line does not pass through the origin confirming the observed behavior of the Weber-Morris model. Thus, particle diffusion is the most probable operating mechanism and does not control the kinetics of benzene sorption i.e. external mass transport mainly governs the rate-limiting process.

Mechanism of benzene removal by RHC :

It is of great importance to reveal the dominant adsorption mechanism of benzene on RHC even though it is not straightforward. In the adsorption mechanism of aromatic compounds in liquid phase on activated carbons there are two main types of interactions : electrostatic and dispersive⁴⁴.

Since benzene is in the molecular form in solution, the adsorption mechanism may be occurs by dispersive attraction between the π orbital of graphene sheet on the carbon basal planes and the electronic density in the benzene aromatic rings (π - π interactions)⁴⁵. Furthermore, the electrostatic interaction between benzene molecules and RHC surface may also explain the observation of high benzene adsorption on RHC. Jankowska and co-workers suggested that benzene can also be adsorbed on the weakly acidic or nonacidic oxygen groups by the interaction of benzene ring π electrons with the positive charge of those groups which results in more electrostatic attraction and thus leads to a higher benzene adsorption.

Comparative study :

The comparisons in benzene equilibrium adsorption capacity of various adsorbents including single-walled CNT (SWCNT), multiwalled CNT (MWCNT), PAC, GAC, montmorillonite, zeolite and activated carbon fiber (ACF) conducted in this study or reported in the literature are given in Table 3. The present RHC shows better performance of benzene adsorption than many types of adsorbents. This suggests that the RHC are efficient benzene adsorbents. Since the production and the use of RHC have very low cost, thus, the RHC possess good potential for benzene removal in wastewater treatment.

Table 3. Comparisons in benzene adsorption of various adsorbents

Adsorbent	q_e (mg/g)	Ref.
RHC	365	This study
AC	274.7	46
CNT	247.87	47
GAC	217.32	47
GAC	183.3	45
Synthetic zeolites	150.42	48
GAC	114.4	45
ACF	66	49
SWCNT	60.1	50
PAC	40	51
MWCNT	36.2	50
Montmorillonite	28	51
Zeolite	27	51
Synthetic zeolites	14.95	52

Conclusion

The adsorption of benzene using activated carbon prepared from rice husk (RHC) was investigated. The kinetic study of benzene on RHC was performed based on pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order, Elovich and intraparticle diffusion equations. The adsorption kinetics data followed pseudo-second order kinetic model suggesting chemisorption nature of the process. Intraparticle diffusion model confirmed that intraparticle is not a fully operative mechanism, whereas the Boyed model suggested film diffusion to be the rate limiting step. A comparative study on BTEX adsorption revealed that the RHC show superior adsorption performance as compared to many types of other adsorbents conducted reported in the literature. Overall, RHC may be used as a low-cost, natu-

ral and abundant source for the removal of benzene from water and wastewater. Further studies on quantitative characterization of this adsorbent and involved mechanisms, and feasibility of using this adsorbent for other organic and inorganics for possible industrial application are needed.

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